

TRIGONAMETRIK FUNKSIYALARNI BESSEL FUNKSIYALARI YORDAMIDA QATORGA YOYISH

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Ushbu ishda 2-tartibli oddiy differensial tenglama uchun Dirixlening spektral masalasini ko'ramiz. (*) xos qiymatlar, xos funksiyalarni topamiz va shu funksiya yordamida ba'zi funksiyalarni qatorga yoyamiz.

D_λ **masala.** λ parametrning shunday qiymatlarini topish kerakki,

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left(r \frac{dR(r)}{dr} \right) + \lambda r R(r) = 0, \quad 0 < r < a, \quad (1)$$

tenglamaning quyidagi

$$R(0) = O(1), \quad R(a) = 0, \quad (2)$$

chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi trivial bo'lmagan yechimi mavjud bo'lsin.

Bu yerda katta $O(1)$ belgisi [1, c15] funksiyani qandaydir o'zgarmas son dan kichikligini bildiradi.

Qidirilayotgan λ parametrning qiymatlari (1), (2) masalaning xos qiymatlari, ularga mos keluvchi trivial bo'lmagan yechimlar esa xos funksiyalar deyiladi.

(1) tenglamaning umumiy yechimini topish uchun, $x = \sqrt{\lambda}r$ $\lambda > 0$ almashtirish bajaramiz. Natijada Bessel tenglamasi deb ataluvchi:

$$\frac{d^2 R}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{x} \frac{dR}{dx} + R = 0 \quad (3)$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

(3) tenglamaning umumiy yechimi ko'rinishidan [2] foydalanib, (1) tenglamaning umumiy yechimini quyidagi ko'rinishda hosil qilamiz:

$$R(r) = A J_0(\sqrt{\lambda}r) + B Y_0(\sqrt{\lambda}r), \quad (4)$$

bu yerda $J_0(x)$ va $Y_0(x)$ – mos holda 0-tartibli birinchi va ikkinchi tur Bessel funksiyalari. A va B- ixtiyoriy o'zgarmas sonlar.

Bu (4) tenglamaning umumiy yechimini (2) shartning birinчисiga bo'y sindiramiz.

$$\lim_{r \rightarrow 0} J_0(\sqrt{\lambda}r) = 1, \quad \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} Y_0(\sqrt{\lambda}r) = -\infty,$$

tenglikni inobatga olsak, quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$R(0) = A \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} J_0(\sqrt{\lambda}r) + B \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} Y_0(\sqrt{\lambda}r) = A \cdot 1 + B \cdot (-\infty)$$

(2) shartning birinchisiga asosan $A \neq 0, B = 0$ deb hisoblaymiz. Natijada bizda (1) tenglamaning (2) shartning birinchisini qanoatlantiruvchi yechimni hosil qilamiz:

$$R(r) = A \cdot J_0(\sqrt{\lambda}r). \quad (5)$$

(5) $\Rightarrow$ (2) shartni ikkinchisiga bo'y sindiramiz. Ya'ni

$$R(a) = A \cdot J_0(\sqrt{\lambda}a) = 0$$

$A \neq 0$ ligidan tenglamaning ikki tomonini A ga bo'lamiz. Natijada λ parametrga nisbatan quyidagi tenglamaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$J_0(\sqrt{\lambda}a) = 0 \quad (6)$$

Bilamizki, $l > -1$ qiymatlarida $J_l(z)$ Bessel funksiyasi sanoqli "0" qiymatlarni qabul qiladi va bular haqiqiy bir-biriga qarama-qarshi ishorali ildizlarga ega [2, c528]. (4) tenglamada $\sqrt{\lambda}a = \gamma$ belgilashni qabul qilib, quyidagi ko'rinishga kelamiz:

$$J_0(\gamma) = 0 \quad (7)$$

$\lambda > 0$ ligidan, γ - haqiqiy; bu (7) tenglamaning haqiqiy ildizlarini $J_0(\gamma)$ funksiyasining grafik ko'rinishiga qarab mavjudligini asoslash mumkin.

$$\sqrt{\lambda}a = \gamma_n, \quad \lambda_n = \left(\frac{\gamma_n}{a}\right)^2, \quad n \in N.$$

Demak, xos qiymatlar quyidagi ko'rinishda:

$$\lambda_1 = \left(\frac{\gamma_1}{a}\right)^2, \lambda_2 = \left(\frac{\gamma_2}{a}\right)^2, \lambda_3 = \left(\frac{\gamma_3}{a}\right)^2, \dots, \lambda_n = \left(\frac{\gamma_n}{a}\right)^2, \dots, \quad (8)$$

$\lambda = \lambda_n$ da (5) tenglamada quyidagi xos funksiyalarni topishimiz mumkin bo'ladi:

$$R_1(r) = J_0\left(\gamma_1 \frac{r}{a}\right), R_2(r) = J_0\left(\gamma_2 \frac{r}{a}\right), \dots, R_n(r) = J_0\left(\gamma_n \frac{r}{a}\right), \dots \quad (9)$$

A.Q.Urinov ustozning Maxsus funksiyalar va maxsus operatorlar kitobidan ma'lumki (9) funksiyalar sistemasi $L_2(0, a)$ fazoda, r vazn bilan to'la va ortonormal hisoblanadi, ya'ni:

$$(R_1, R_2) = \int_0^a r \cdot R_1(r) R_2(r) dr = \int_0^a r \cdot J_0\left(\frac{\gamma_1 r}{a}\right) J_0\left(\frac{\gamma_2 r}{a}\right) dr = 0$$

$$\|R_1\|^2 = (R_1, R_1) = \int_0^a r \cdot R_1^2(r) dr = \int_0^a r \cdot J_0^2\left(\frac{\gamma_1 r}{a}\right) dr = \frac{1}{2} a^2 J_1^2(\gamma_1).$$

Endi keyingi masalani ko'rib chiqamiz: Dirixle masalasining xos funksiyalari, ya'ni (9) haqiqiy funksiyalar sistemasi bo'yicha 1) $f(r) = \sin\left(\frac{\pi r}{2a}\right)$ va 2) $f(r) = \cos\left(\frac{\pi r}{2a}\right)$ funksiyalarni $[0, a]$ oraliqda qatorga yoyish, masalasi bilan tanishamiz.

1.1 Yoyish koeffitsientini topamiz

$$f(r) = \sin\left(\frac{\pi r}{2a}\right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n J_0\left(\frac{\gamma_n r}{a}\right)$$

formulaga asosan

$$C_n = \frac{2}{a^2 J_1^2(\gamma_n)} \int_0^a r f(r) J_0(\gamma_n r/a) dr. \quad (10)$$

(10) integralni hisoblashda (1) tenglamadan foydalanish qulay hisoblanadi.

$$r J_0\left(\frac{\gamma_n r}{a}\right) dr = -\left(\frac{a}{\gamma_n}\right)^2 d\left(r \frac{d}{dr} J_0\left(\frac{\gamma_n r}{a}\right)\right). \quad (11)$$

(11) tenglamani (10) ga qo'yib bo'laklab integrallasak, bizda

$$C_n = -\frac{4\pi}{a(4\gamma_n^2 - \pi^2) J_1^2(\gamma_n)} \int_0^a \cos\left(\frac{\pi r}{2a}\right) J_0\left(\frac{\gamma_n r}{a}\right) dr,$$

natijada,

$$\sin\left(\frac{\pi r}{2a}\right) = -\frac{4\pi}{a} \int_0^a \cos\left(\frac{\pi r}{2a}\right) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{J_0^2(\gamma_n r/a)}{(4\gamma_n^2 - \pi^2) J_1^2(\gamma_n)} dr.$$

1.2 Yoyish koeffitsientini topamiz

$$f(r) = \cos\left(\frac{\pi r}{2a}\right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n J_0\left(\frac{\gamma_n r}{a}\right)$$

formulaga asosan

$$C_n = \frac{2}{a^2 J_1^2(\gamma_n)} \int_0^a r f(r) J_0(\gamma_n r/a) dr. \quad (10)$$

(10) integralni hisoblashda (1) tenglamadan foydalanish qulay hisoblanadi.

$$r J_0\left(\frac{\gamma_n r}{a}\right) dr = -\left(\frac{a}{\gamma_n}\right)^2 d\left(r \frac{d}{dr} J_0\left(\frac{\gamma_n r}{a}\right)\right). \quad (11)$$

(11) tenglamani (10) ga qo'yib bo'laklab integrallasak, bizda

$$C_n = \frac{4\pi}{a(4\gamma_n^2 - \pi^2) J_1^2(\gamma_n)} \int_0^a \sin\left(\frac{\pi r}{2a}\right) J_0\left(\frac{\gamma_n r}{a}\right) dr,$$

natijada,

$$\cos\left(\frac{\pi r}{2a}\right) = \frac{4\pi}{a} \int_0^a \sin\left(\frac{\pi r}{2a}\right) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{J_0^2(\gamma_n r/a)}{(4\gamma_n^2 - \pi^2)J_1^2(\gamma_n)}.$$

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